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J Recent Adv Agr 2014, 2(7): 285-289

Effect of Inter Plant Distance on Seed Cotton Yield and its Component in *G. Hirsutum* L.

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Abstract

This study was conducted to compare the seed cotton yield and its components over cotton leaf curl virus (CLCuV) invasions of advanced cotton genotypes (VH-306 and VH-311) under different plant spacings (15.0, 30.0, 45.0 and 60.0 cm) at Cotton Research Station (CRS), Vehari, Pakistan, during 2013. The objective of the study was to determine overall yields of modern varieties under different plant spacings. The results specify that cotton sown at 60 cm plant distance performed better and produced maximum seed cotton yield. The cotton cultivars were also differed considerably in their plant growth and VH-306 showed superiority over another in all plant spacing. Plant spacing had significant effects on the avg. number of bolls per plant, avg. boll weight, avg. seed cotton yield and non-significantly effects for CLCuV infestations. However, cotton varieties severely affected by CLCuV can be managed by increasing plant spacing to optimum level (60cm). Plant population was statistically similar for both cotton genotypes. In summary, cotton genotype VH-306 was recommended for prime harvesting and produced higher seed cotton yield when sown with 60 cm plant spacing under CLCuV hotspot condition of Vehari district.

Keywords: Spacing, seed cotton yield, CLCuV infestation.

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Received on: 09 Jul 2014

Revised on: 19 Jul 2014

Accepted on: 26 Jul 2014

Online Published on: 30 Jul 2014

Introduction

Cotton is not only the principal cash crop but also considered as kigpin in Pakistan economy. It occupied about 2.835 million hectares with production of 13 million bales with average production of 769 kg/ha. It accounts for 7.0 percent of value added in agriculture and 1.5% of GDP (Anonymous 2013-14). Producers are persistently searching for ways to compensate increases in production cost. Though research has been steered for the past century in these areas where there is still need for improvements. In cotton plant spacing has effects on its overall seed cotton yield and plant growth. One of the choices for maximizing yield per unit area is optimum plant population and it varies from plant genotype to genotype. Every variety has its own plant to plant space requirements. Maximum yield can be achieved by maintaining an optimal plant population, according to plant morphological characteristics. A significant plant spacing was known for seed cotton yield. Hussain *et al.*, (2000) described that 30 cm spacing between plants increased number of bolls per plant, plant height and average boll weight as compared to 10 cm and 20 cm. Muhammad *et al.*, (2002) determined that the boll weight decreases by increasing plant population. Cotton grown in 22.5cm plant spacing had higher yield as compared to 15cm and 30cm (Ali *et al.*, 2009; Awan *et al.*, 2011). El Naim *et al.*, (2013) stated that 75cm plant spacing cause significant increase sympodial branches, boll weight, total number of bolls and seed cotton yield. Extensive work on comparisons of varieties of the cotton crop is available world over. Keeping this in view, the present study was therefore designed to determine the effect of plant spacing on the yield of recently approved (VH-306 and VH-311) varieties of cotton.

Materials and Methods

A field experiment was conducted to evaluate the effect of plant spacing on the yield of recently evolved varieties of cotton at Cotton Research Station Vehari, Pakistan, during May, 2013. The Experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with split plot arrangement having

three replications and a net plot size of 9.0 m x 3.0 m. The varieties were kept in the main plot and plant spacing in subplots. Two varieties VH-306 and VH-311 were sown at four different plant spacing 15cm, 30cm, 45cm and 60cm. Cotton crop was sown at 75 cm spaced rows manually with a single row hand drill. The whole of the phosphorous at the rate of 75 kg ha⁻¹ was applied at the time of sowing in the form of SSP while the nitrogen at the rate of 115 kg/ha was applied in the form of Urea in three splits, 1/3 at the time of first flowering 1/3 nitrogen at peak flowering and 1/3 at peak boll formation. Thinning was done at four leaf stage to maintain a plant to plant distance as per treatment. All other agronomic practices were kept normal and uniform for all the treatments. Yield contributing parameters was recorded and the data collected were analyzed statistically by using Fisher's analysis of variance techniques and differences among treatment means were compared using least significant difference test at 5% probability level (Steel *et al.*, 1997).

Result and Discussion

The data on growth and yield performance of cotton varieties are affected by plant spacing revealed highly significant differences in all the growth and yield component.

Chracters of Different Cotton Varieties under Varying Plant Spacing

Number of bolls per plant is an important yield contributing parameter (Table-1). Data from the table illustrated, that by increasing plant spacing there was a significant increase in the number of bolls per plant. Maximum number of bolls per plant (47) were recorded in case of 60 cm plant spacing against the minimum (14) in 15 cm plant spacing of VH-306. Similarly, VH-311 was also recorded for maximum number of bolls per plant (43) in 60 cm plant spacing (Figure-1). Increase in number of bolls per plant with increasing plant spacing can be attributed to more availability of space, less competition and more number of sympodial branches per plant. These results are in line with Those of Ali *et al.*, (2009) who specified that increase in density decreases number of bolls per

plant. Reduced competition among plants along with more available space enabled the plants to uptake more water and nutrients to produce more

sympodial and monopodial branches that ultimately resulted in more number of bolls per plant (Nadeem *et al.*, 2010; Iqbal *et al.*, 2012).

Table 1: No. of bolls plant⁻¹.

Varieties	15cm	30cm	45cm	60cm	Mean of varieties
VH-306	13.9	23.9	26.97	46.97	27.935
VH-311	13.1	23.97	33.07	43	28.285
Mean of spacing	13.5	23.935	30.02	44.985	
LSD (0.05)			0.5481		

Boll weight is an important yield contributing parameter (Table-2). It is evident from the data that average boll weight affected significantly by plant spacing, but higher CLCuV infestation ultimately reduced the boll weight. Statistically maximum average boll weight (3.92 gm) was obtained in 45 cm plant spacing against the minimum value of (3.34 gm) in case of 30 cm plant spacing of cotton genotype VH-306 (Figure-2). Similarly, in case of VH-311 maximum boll weight (3.3g) was found in case of 30cm plant spacing (77.9% CLCuV infestation) and minimum average boll weight

(3.1gm) was observed in 60cm plant spacing. However, average boll weight was reduced (3.45g) in case of 60cm plant spacing that might be due to higher CLCuV infestation (95.07%). The reason was 60 cm plant spacing promoted better plant growth that eventually encourages CLCuV incidence. The greater average boll weight at higher plant spacing might be due to less competition and availability of resources but CLCuV intensity also effected nutrients absorption of plants which negatively affected boll weight and eventually overall seed cotton yield.

Table 2: Av. Boll weight (g).

Varieties	15cm	30cm	45cm	60cm	Mean of varieties
VH-306	3.49	3.34	3.92	3.45	3.55
VH-311	3.23	3.3	3.26	3.1	3.2225
Mean of spacing	3.36	3.32	3.59	3.275	
LSD (0.05)			0.1184		

These results are in support with those of Hussain *et al.*, (2000) and Boquet (2005) who described that by increasing plant density average boll weight decreases. Different varieties also varied significantly for their average boll weight.

Muhammad *et al.*, (2002) and Nadeem *et al.*, (2010) explained enhanced average boll weight with increased plant spacing. Cotton genotypes showed tolerance against CLCuV infestation while different plant spacings also affected significantly (Table-3).

Table 3: CLCuV Percentage.

Varieties	15cm	30cm	45cm	60cm	Mean of varieties
VH-306	38.43	79.93	89.87	95.07	75.825
VH-311	50.37	77.9	85.97	92.13	76.5925
Mean of spacing	44.4	78.915	87.92	93.6	
LSD (0.05)			22.272		

Cotton genotype VH-306 and VH-311 had a significantly lower CLCuV infestation throughout the growing period but better plant growth

encourages higher CLCuV incidence. Cotton sowing with narrow plant spacing (15 cm spaced plants) had a less infestation than wider plant

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spacing (Figure-3). However, narrow plant spacing was very effective in managing CLCuV incidence, particularly in late sown cotton. Lower CLCuV infestation in both cotton genotypes might be due to their better genetic makeup (Iqbal and Khan 2010). Nonsignificant effects of plant spacing on CLCuV infestation might be due to the genetic character of genotypes that cannot be controlled by plant spacing (Iqbal *et al.*, 2007). Moreover, cotton genotypes VH-306 and VH-311 resulted in higher seed cotton yield by producing a higher number of

bolts per plant of heavier weight and more CLCV infestation due to wider spacing that ensured plant growth which also encourage CLCuV infestation.

The seed cotton yield is the combined effect of various yield components under particular environmental conditions (Table-4). It is obvious from the data that varying plant spacing had a significant effect on seed cotton yield. Significantly maximum seed cotton yield (2792.5 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded when the crop was sown at 60 cm plants to plant spacing.

Table 4: Cotton Seed Yield (Kg ha⁻¹).

Varieties	15cm	30cm	45cm	60cm	Mean of varieties
VH-306	2652.6	2505.5	2466	2792.5	2604.15
VH-311	2132.3	2354.8	2255.5	2362	2276.15
Mean of spacing	2392.45	2430.15	2360.75	2577.25	
LSD (0.05)			398.35		

Effect of Inter plant spacing (15.0cm, 30.0cm, 45.0cm and 60cm) on seed cotton yield of cotton genotype VH-306 and VH-311.

However, minimum yield (2132.3 kg ha⁻¹) was obtained in the case of 15 cm plant spacing for VH-311 (Figure-4). This decrease in yield may be due to overpopulation and more competition between the plants for light and nutrients. Similarly, increase in humidity also cause fruit shedding. On the other hand, CLCuV infestation also affects the uptake of nutrients and minerals which affect the yield contributing component. The Higher seed cotton yield with narrow plant spacing was the direct result of higher plant density. Sarkar and Malik (2004) and Somro *et al.*, (2005) reported that the wider and optimum plant spacing enables plants to capture solar radiation which in turn increase the photosynthesis of the plants and ultimately seed cotton yield.

Conclusion

The experimental results for varietal performance showed tolerance and recover noticeably against CLCuV invasion, and plant spacing of 60 cm significantly enhanced overall yield and yield parameters under the hotspot condition of Vehari district.

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